

PROCESSING OF PYRITE CONCENTRATES WITH THE EXTRACTION OF NON-FERROUS METALS: NICKEL AND COBALT TECHNOLOGY ELABORATION

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ABSTRACT. The paper presents the results of the development of a technology for processing of pyrite concentrates with the extraction of non-ferrous metals, iron and sulphur using the technology of two-stage dissociating roasting with hydrometallurgical processing of cinder. Hydrometallurgical processing of cinder was studied. It comprised of two steps - cinder leaching and extraction for processing multi-component solutions. Based on the results of laboratory tests, balance experiments were conducted on the chemical enrichment of nickel-poor and cobalt-pyrite concentrates. The experiments included (i) Thermal decomposition of pyrite concentrate at a temperature of 660 - 700° C and a duration of 60 minutes, an oxygen flow rate of 30-50% of the stoichiometric; (ii) Leaching of the cinder with a HCl solution at a temperature of 90°C, liquid: solid = 8:1, pH 2,7 and a duration of 60 minutes; (iii) Filtration of pulp and precipitation of nickel and cobalt from solutions with iron sulphide. During leaching, mainly iron is transferred to the solution; nickel and cobalt remain in a small amount of cake (the cake weight is reduced by almost ten times compared to the thermal decomposition product). As a result, up to 99% of non-ferrous metals are extracted into the concentrate, and the solution becomes more concentrated in iron.

Keywords: pyrite concentrates, sulphidising roasting, nickel and cobalt, hydrometallurgical processing

Introduction

The processing of pyrite and pyrrhotite concentrates is carried out in Canada, Finland and Zambia. In Canada, oxidative roasting is used, followed by cinder processing to recover cobalt, nickel, and iron pellets. In Canada, the initial product is subjected to oxidative roasting, followed by processing of the cinder to recover cobalt, nickel and obtain iron-containing pellets (Morcali et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019). In Finland and Zambia, the original concentrate is subjected to sulfatizing or dissociating roasting, followed by hydrometallurgical processing of the cinder. The residual concentration of cobalt in the waste cakes is over 0.4 % in Zambia and about 0,2 % in Finland (Güntner, et al., 2012).

With an initial cobalt content of about 3% in Zambian concentrates and about 1,2% in pyrrhotite concentrates in Finland, the recovery of cobalt is 80–85%. The residual concentration of cobalt in dump cakes is over 0,4% in Zambia and about 0,2% in Finland (Güntner, et al., 2012).

In general, the problem of processing stale tailings is a global problem, and the main task is to extract economically valuable metals: cobalt, nickel and copper (Wang et al., 2019), (Zhang et. al., 2013). Today more than 40% of cobalt is extracted from such raw materials. In Kazakhstan, the market for extracting cobalt from stale tailings is practically undeveloped. And the demand for nickel and cobalt is about 3–5 thousand tons per year.

World production of primary nickel in all forms in 2019, according to analysts at Wood Mackenzie, amounted to 2,235 thousand tonnes, including 1,153 thousand tonnes of nickel (51,5%) - in ferronickel and nickel iron alloys, the data are published by Li and co-authors (2015). The world production of refined cobalt, according to estimates by the Cobalt Institute (CI) - (formerly the Cobalt Development Institute), amounted to 124,3 thousand tonnes in 2019, which is 7,4 thousand tonnes more than in 2018 (Selivanov et al., 2019).

The main part of cobalt is used in the production of batteries (~76 thousand tonnes in 2019) and super-alloys

(~17,6 thousand tonnes in 2019), and the level of production of rechargeable energy sources and, accordingly, the consumption of cobalt is growing steadily. So, if in 1995 the demand for cobalt in this consumption sector was estimated at 700 tonnes, then in 2014 it approached 40 thousand tonnes, and in 2019 - 76 thousand tonnes (60% of world demand). All other areas accounted for about 26% of global demand (Sadykhov et al., 2020).

The Republic of Kazakhstan possesses huge amounts of raw materials, including nickel and cobalt ores. For example, the reserves of the Shevchenko deposit alone for nickel are 403,9 thousand tonnes, for cobalt – 23,4 thousand tonnes. The Gornostayevskoye deposit (Kazakhstan) contains 500 thousand tonnes of nickel reserves and 32,4 thousand tonnes of cobalt. Tailings from Sokolovsko-Sarbaiskoe mining and processing production association (Sokolovsko-Sarbaiskoe gornobogatitelnoe proizvodstvennoe obединenie (SSGPO JSC)) represent technogenic raw materials containing more than 7 thousand tonnes of nickel and 14 thousand tonnes of cobalt per year. Despite the growing global trend in the consumption of nickel and cobalt in Kazakhstan, the extraction of these metals from domestic ores has not yet been organised, (Motovilov et al., 2018). The organisation of our own industrial production of nickel and cobalt from a significant amount of nickel- and cobalt-containing raw materials and man-made materials available in Kazakhstan is undoubtedly an urgent task.

At SSGPO JSC (Kazakhstan), in the course of many years of processing iron ores, a significant amount of tailings has accumulated, which are currently an additional potential source of raw materials. When processing sulphide-magnetite ores of the SSGPO JSC, waste is generated in the form of wet magnetic separation tailings, which in the amount of 8 million tonnes per year are stored in dumps. Tailings of wet magnetic separation (WMS) contain sulphur, cobalt, non-ferrous and precious metals, the production of which in annual terms can be approximately 400 thousand tonnes of sulphur (S), 400 thousand tonnes of iron (Fe), 1.2 thousand tonnes of cobalt (Co), 3 thousand tonnes copper (Cu), 0,5 thousand tonnes of

nickel (Ni). At the moment, there are about 400 million tonnes of tailings suitable for processing. Precious metals are concentrated in old stale WMS tailings.

The research presented here is devoted to the development of a technology for processing pyrite concentrates with the extraction of non-ferrous metals, iron and sulphur using the technology of two-stage dissociating roasting with hydrometallurgical processing of cinder.

The aim of the work is to test the technology for processing old and fresh tailings of magnetic separation, to confirm the possibility of their economically feasible processing, to test the technology for processing pyrite concentrates, with the extraction of cobalt and nickel into commercial products.

Thermodynamic research

For the processing of Kazakhstani raw materials, the most acceptable is the use of combined technologies, including pyrometallurgical processing (smelting of oxidised or roasting of sulphide materials) with subsequent chemical enrichment of the products obtained by processes including acid leaching followed by precipitation from solutions of nickel and cobalt sulphides.

In order to find optimum treatment conditions thermodynamic calculations are needed. The results of thermodynamic studies of the selected processes are presented further.

Thermodynamics of pyrometallurgical processes

Chemical enrichment can be carried out by selective leaching or selective precipitation of metal compounds. The process can involve raw materials with preliminary pyrometallurgical preparation or without preparation. To substantiate the process of chemical enrichment, we have performed a thermodynamic analysis of systems including nickel, cobalt, iron, sulphur, oxygen under the conditions of pyro- and hydrometallurgical processing. The ways of sulphidising roasting were published earlier (Merkibaev et. al., 2018).

Using the thermodynamic calculation programme HSC Chemistry 5 from Outokumpu, we calculated the thermodynamic characteristics of the main reactions and built isothermal sections of phase equilibrium diagrams in the systems Fe – O – S, Ni – O – S, Co – O – S at temperatures of 800–1100 K. It has been established that with an increase in the oxygen pressure in the system at a temperature of 900 K and a partial pressure of sulphur dioxide close to atmospheric $p_{\text{PSO}_2} = 0$ pyrite undergoes the following transformations - $\text{FeS}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 \rightarrow \text{FeSO}_4 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$.

With a decrease in the concentration of SO_2 , the transformation of iron disulphide takes place with the successive formation of lower iron sulphides: $\text{FeS}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_7\text{S}_4 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_{0,877}\text{S} \rightarrow \text{FeS}$, these data are corresponding to (Bastow, et.al, 2018). Under the conditions of thermal treatment of pyrite in the presence of roasting gases, the aforementioned lower iron sulphides are formed, as well as Fe_3O_4 and possibly FeSO_4 .

For the thermodynamic analysis of the process of heat treatment of nickel-cobalt-containing sulphide raw materials, we have performed calculations of the Gibbs energy of the probable basic reactions (Table 1).

When roasting FeS_2 in the presence of a limited amount of oxygen, iron sulphides of various compositions can be obtained by reactions (1-4): $\text{Fe}_{0,877}\text{S}$, FeS , Fe_2S_3 , Fe_7S_8 within

the homogeneity region. In addition, according to reactions (4-9), depending on the roasting conditions, interconversions of the above iron sulphides can occur.

Nickel and cobalt sulphides behave in a similar way, so according to reactions 10 and 11, cobalt disulphide can pass into $\text{CoS}_{0,89}$ and CoS , according to reactions 15,16 - nickel disulphide passes into Ni_3S_2 and Ni_3S_4 , according to reactions 12-14, 17- 19, the transformation of cobalt and nickel sulphides occurs within the homogeneity region. With an excess of oxygen, oxygen-containing compounds of iron, nickel and cobalt are formed: metal oxides and sulphates.

Thus, based on the phase diagrams of Fe (Ni, Co) -S systems, it can be argued that, due to the presence of a wide homogeneity range, it is possible to ensure, under heat treatment conditions (700–1100 K), the formation of low-sulphur iron compounds of a wide range of compositions, as well as cobalt and nickel of variable composition, these are corresponding to (Zhang et.al., 2019).

Table 1. Thermodynamic analysis of possible reactions of dissociating roasting of materials

Chemical reaction	ΔG° , kJ/mol	
	273 K	900 K
1. $\text{FeS}_2 + 1/2\text{O}_2 = 1/2\text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 + 1/2\text{SO}_2$	-130,30	-143,19
2. $\text{FeS}_2 + 0,86\text{O}_2 = 1,14 \text{Fe}_{0,877}\text{S} + 0,86 \text{SO}_2$	-208,20	-245,42
3. $\text{FeS}_2 + \text{O}_2 = \text{FeS} + \text{SO}_2$	-241,97	-280,78
4. $\text{FeS}_2 + 6/7\text{O}_2 = 1/7\text{Fe}_7\text{S}_8 + 6/7\text{SO}_2$	-203,90	-237,17
5. $\text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 + 5/7\text{O}_2 = 2/7\text{Fe}_7\text{S}_8 + 5/7\text{SO}_2$	-147,20	-187,95
6. $\text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 + 0,719\text{O}_2 = 2,281\text{Fe}_{0,877}\text{S} + 0,719 \text{SO}_2$	-155,60	-204,28
7. $\text{Fe}_2\text{S}_3 + \text{O}_2 = 2\text{FeS} + \text{SO}_2$	-223,34	-275,17
8. $\text{Fe}_7\text{S}_8 + \text{O}_2 = 7\text{FeS} + \text{SO}_2$	-266,49	-305,26
9. $\text{Fe}_{0,877}\text{S} + 0,123\text{O}_2 = 0,877\text{FeS} + 0,123\text{SO}_2$	-29,66	-31,05
10. $\text{CoS}_2 + \text{O}_2 = \text{CoS} + \text{SO}_2$	-250,42	-268,37
11. $\text{CoS}_2 + 1,11\text{O}_2 = \text{CoS}_{0,89} + 1,11\text{SO}_2$	-279,36	-295,41
12. $\text{CoS}_{1,333} + 0,333\text{O}_2 = \text{CoS} + 0,333\text{SO}_2$	-80,14	-86,00
13. $\text{CoS}_{1,333} + 0,443\text{O}_2 = \text{CoS}_{0,89} + 0,443\text{SO}_2$	-109,07	-113,03
14. $\text{CoS} + 0,11\text{O}_2 = \text{CoS}_{0,89} + 0,11\text{SO}_2$	-28,94	-27,04
15. $\text{NiS}_2 + 2/3\text{O}_2 = 1/3\text{Ni}_3\text{S}_4 + 2/3\text{SO}_2$	-172,08	-183,36
16. $\text{NiS}_2 + 4/3\text{O}_2 = 1/3\text{Ni}_3\text{S}_2 + 4/3\text{SO}_2$	-344,68	-360,84
17. $\text{Ni}_3\text{S}_4 + \text{O}_2 = 3\text{NiS} + \text{SO}_2$	-263,38	-272,94
18. $\text{Ni}_3\text{S}_4 + 2\text{O}_2 = \text{Ni}_3\text{S}_2 + 2\text{SO}_2$	-517,79	-532,46
19. $\text{NiS} + 1/3\text{O}_2 = 1/3\text{SO}_2 + 1/3\text{Ni}_3\text{S}_2$	-84,81	-86,50

Thermodynamics of selective sulphide precipitation

The values of the solubility products of iron, nickel and cobalt sulphides, the effect of acidity and oxidation potential of the system on the behaviour of sulphides during hydrometallurgical processes allow us to conclude that it is

possible to selectively dissolve iron sulphides from a mixture of nickel, cobalt and iron sulphides, and a possibility exists of selective precipitation of Ni and Co sulphides from ferrous solutions.

Based on the Pourbaix diagrams, it is possible to recommend carrying out the leaching process in the pH range of 0-2,5. In this case, nickel and cobalt can pass into the solution, which subsequently, in accordance with the values of the solubility product, can be precipitated in the form of sulphides, Figures 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. "Potential - pH" diagram of the Ni-S-H₂O system

Fig. 2. "Potential - pH" diagram of the Co-S-H₂O system

Materials and methods

Materials

In order to use the tailings accumulated at SSGPO JSC as an additional potential source of raw materials, it became necessary to conduct research to develop a technology for their processing using flotation and magnetic separation processes.

We received two samples for the study, represented by old stale and current tailings of WMS of SSGPO JSC. The mass of the sample of current tailings was 500 kg with a maximum size of individual grains 3-4 mm. The sample weight of old stale tailings was 540 kg with the maximum size of individual grains up to 5 mm.

The chemical composition of the original current WMS tailings was, in %: Fe_{total} - 12,62; Cu - 0,05; Co - 0,013; Ni - 0,0081; S_{total} - 3,46; Pb - 0,019; Zn - 0,069; SiO₂ - 40,23; Al₂O₃ - 18,97; CaO - 12,59; MgO - 4,72; TiO₂ - 0,59; As - 0,006 and other elements.

Flotation experiments

Laboratory flotation studies were carried out on standard laboratory flotation machines with chamber volumes of 3, 1,5, 1, 0,5, and 0,25 litres. When performing studies on flotation, the following reagents were used: butyl xanthate - collector (activity 84,5%); T-80 - foaming agent (100% activity); flotation was carried out with tap water at pH - 7-7,5. Experimental work was carried out in a closed cycle (7 samples).

Thermal decomposition of pyrite concentrate

Thermal decomposition was carried out in a fixed-bed reactor, a sample was placed in a quartz tube, closed on both sides with plugs, and the temperature was automatically maintained at a given accuracy. The resulting product was analysed by the X-ray phase method for composition.

Leaching of thermally decomposed pyrite concentrate

The study of the leaching process was carried out with a pyrite concentrate thermally decomposed at a temperature of 973 K for 30 minutes in glass flasks with a reflux condenser and a stirrer. The stirrer rotation speed in all experiments was kept constant. A sample weighing 10-20 grams was loaded into a flask and filled with a solvent. The flask was placed in a water thermostat, the temperature in which was maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 0,2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The duration of the experiments was counted from the moment the specified temperature was reached.

At the end of the experiment, the solid phase was separated from the liquid and washed with slightly acidified water. Then both phases were analysed for the content of iron, nickel and cobalt.

A preliminary study was made of the efficiency of using various leaching reagents at different amount, which were solutions of ferrous chloride, hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid, and a mixture of hydrochloric acid with magnesium chloride. Comparison of various reagents showed that the greatest extraction of cobalt and iron into solution is achieved when a mixture of hydrochloric acid and magnesium chloride is used as a solvent.

The concentration of hydrochloric acid used for dissolution was taken on the basis of operating conditions in a closed cycle with the possibility of solvent regeneration, as well as obtaining the smallest volumes of solutions. With the hydrothermal decomposition of chloride salts, hydrochloric acid with a concentration in the range of 250 g/L HCl can be obtained. This concentration of acid provides the receipt of rich solutions close to saturation in iron.

In the second series of experiments, the effect of temperature on the leaching process was studied. The amount of solvent was taken 1,04 times the theoretically required, the leaching time was taken equal to 2 hours.

Extraction methodology and experiment

The objectives of this study are to establish the optimal conditions for the selective and combined extraction of cobalt and nickel by extraction with an extractant CYANEX 272, re-extraction of metals from solutions of complex composition, as well as the conditions for the extraction of impurities of iron and cobalt from solutions.

We used the obtained solutions after one-stage leaching of thermally decomposed pyrite-cobalt concentrate, containing about 190 g/L of iron and about 500 mg/L of nickel and cobalt. Also, as comparative experiments, the salts CoSO₄·7H₂O and

NiSO₄•7H₂O were used to prepare synthetic solutions. The required pH value was maintained for 5-90 min, then the pH value changed slightly.

The extraction was carried out on an EL-1 laboratory extractor with stirring and regulation of the pH of the solution. The pH of the medium was adjusted using NaOH and H₂SO₄ solutions. The experiments were carried out at room temperature. The extraction results were evaluated by the residual concentration C (in g/L) of metal ions in the raffinate, the distribution coefficient $D = C_{org}/S_{aq}$, the extraction of metals into the organic phase, the separation coefficient $\beta = D_{Me1}/D_{Me2}$.

Re-extraction of metals from the organic phase was carried out with a sulphuric acid solution with a concentration of 100–200 g/L.

Hydrothermal decomposition of ferrous chloride

The optimal decision for the processing of chloride solutions for marketable products obtaining is the hydrothermal decomposition, high-temperature hydrolysis. As a result of precipitation from solutions of nickel and cobalt sulphides, the solution contains, in g/L: Fe - 185 – 195; Ni 0,01 – 0,04; Co 0,005 – 0,01.

The reaction taken as the basis in experiments on high-temperature hydrolysis of FeCl₂•4H₂O crystals is:

For the regeneration of hydrochloric acid, the solutions of ferrous chloride were subjected to hydrothermal decomposition. In general, the temperature conditions for the hydrothermal decomposition of ferrous chloride were studied.

The scheme for studying hydrothermal decomposition is presented in Fig.3.

The calculation of the degree of decomposition was determined by using the amount of hydrochloric acid formed in the temperature range 603-903 K (decomposition of FeCl₂•4H₂O), 453-503 K (decomposition of FeCl₃•6H₂O) and duration up to 180 minutes.

1 - steam generator; 2 - glass tap; 3 - tubular furnace; 4 - quartz reactor; 5 - acid collector; 6 - refrigerator; 7 - burette with NaOH solution

Fig. 3. Installation diagram for hydrothermal decomposition of ferrous chloride

Results and discussion

Flotation experiments

The results of the flotation experiments are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Closed loop experiment indicators (current tailings of WMS), content

Product name	Output, %	Content, %				
		Cu	Co	Ni	Fe	S
Concentrate	7,74	0,56	0,14	0,066	40,83	47,4
Tailings	92,26	0,005	0,002	0,003	9,45	0,19
Total	100,0	0,0480	0,0127	0,0079	11,88	3,84

The yield of the collective concentrate was 7,74% with a copper content of 0,56%, cobalt 0,14%, nickel 0,066%, iron 40,83% and sulphur 47,4%, with the recovery of copper 90,38%, cobalt 85,45%, nickel 64,86%, iron 26,60% and sulphur 95,44%.

Results of thermal decomposition of pyrite concentrate

It has been established that the optimal conditions for the thermal decomposition of pyrite concentrate are the temperature range of 700-800°C and the duration of 30 minutes. When carrying out decomposition under optimal conditions, the concentrate contained, %: 53,5 Fe; 0,14 Co; 0,146 Ni; 30,5 S. Sulphur recovery at a temperature of 700°C is 47,1%.

Results of leaching of thermally decomposed pyrite concentrate

The results of leaching the thermally decomposed pyrite concentrate with acid solutions with a concentration of 0,5N are shown in Table 3 and Fig.4.

In the first series of experiments, the effect of the amount of solvent on concentrate leaching was studied, and the possibility of selective leaching was tested. As can be seen from the data, there is no selection at the boiling point of the solution and lack of acid. There is only some difference in the degree of decomposition of compounds of nickel, cobalt and iron.

Table 3. Results of leaching of pyrite-cobalt concentrate thermally decomposed in vacuum

T, K	The amount of acid, a multiple of stoichiometric, R	T _{leaching} , min	ε _{B solution} , %		
			Fe	Ni	Co
Decomposition with hydrochloric acid					
Influence of the amount of solvent					
379	0,52	120	69,11	60,58	0
379	1,95	120	97,85	100,0	97,82
Influence of temperature					
20	1,04	120	61,98	45,15	45,84
379	1,04	120	97,03	95,18	94,49
Influence of duration					
379	1,04	7,5	83,50	56,93	68,91
379	1,04	240	97,43	95,81	96,54
Decomposition with sulphuric acid					
Influence of the amount of solvent					
379	0,52	120	67,13	59,56	0
379	1,95	120	97,85	96,85	96,80
Influence of temperature					
20	1,04	120	59,91	42,05	40,04
379	1,04	120	95,03	92,08	91,09
Influence of duration					
379	1,04	7,5	81,00	53,93	66,71
379	1,04	240	95,43	92,81	93,54

With an excess of solvent over 4% of the theoretically required amount, the thermally decomposed pyrite concentrate is almost completely leached, and an increase in the amount of solvent mainly affects the recovery of nickel. Thus, leaching of a thermally decomposed concentrate does not require large excess of solvent, all the more so if one performs

countercurrent continuous leaching rather than periodic one-stage leaching.

The research results from studies on the temperature effect on leaching are shown in Fig.4. From the results obtained it follows that the thermally decomposed concentrate is leached relatively easily. The most complete dissolution of the components of the concentrate is achieved at the boiling point of the solutions - at 379 K. There is some difference in the leaching rates of nickel, cobalt and iron. Nickel is leached most slowly. The optimum temperature range for leaching is 353 – 379 K.

Thus, on the basis of the studies carried out, the conditions for carrying out one-stage leaching of thermally decomposed pyrite-cobalt concentrate were determined - temperature 80 – 379 K; duration 2-4 hours, excess solvent 4-5%. Residual acidity under these conditions is 6-8 g/L, the solid yield is 7-9% of the original.

The solutions after leaching contain about 190 g/L of iron and about 500 mg/L of nickel and cobalt.

Under these conditions, the extraction into solution is: cobalt – 92,04–96,54%; iron – 94,03–97,4%; nickel – 95,18–95,81%. The pulp after leaching settles well, filtration proceeds at a high speed.

a

a) - hydrochloric acid;
extraction of 1– iron; 2 - nickel; 3 - cobalt

b

b) - sulphuric acid;
extraction of 1– iron; 2 - nickel; 3 - cobalt

Fig. 4. Influence of leaching duration on metal recovery during leaching of pyrite-cobalt concentrate thermally decomposed in vacuum at the boiling point of the solution and lixiviant consumption equal to 1,04 of the stoichiometrically required

Approbation of extraction technology for the separation of elements, including the processes of refining and concentration of productive solutions

Based on the results of experiments on metal extraction at various pH values of the solution, the dependence of the distribution coefficients of metals on pH (Fig. 5) from individual solutions of salts and from solutions of a mixture of CoSO_4 and NiSO_4 was plotted.

Fig. 5. Dependence of the separation coefficient of metals ($\beta_{\text{Co/Ni}}$) on the pH of the solution

The obtained experimental data indicate that the CYANEX 272 extractant extracts cobalt and nickel ions quite well. The degree of extraction of cobalt from the leach solution reaches 99 % at pH 6.5; the degree of extraction of nickel is 98% at pH 8-8.5. The calculated values of the metal separation coefficient indicate that the optimal pH of the medium for the separation of these metals is pH 5,5, where the metal separation coefficient reaches its maximum value and is 614. An increase in the solution pH leads to an increase in nickel co-extraction.

The re-extraction (with a sulphuric acid solution with a concentration of 160 g/L) was 97% for cobalt and 95% for nickel. As a result, a solution of the composition, mg/L: 470 Co, 23,75 Ni was obtained. Composition of raffinate was, in mg/L: 15 Co, 475 Ni.

Selection of technology for chloride solutions processing

At process temperatures below 603 K, the decomposition of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ practically does not occur, and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ decomposes noticeably at temperatures above 453 K.

The oxidised iron powders obtained as a result of hydrolysis were subjected to a comprehensive certification of their properties.

The end products of high-temperature hydrolysis of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals with incomplete decomposition (no more than 60%) is magnetite, and with more complete decomposition, a mixture of magnetite and hematite powders.

Thus, technological scheme for processing ferrous chloride solutions has been elaborated, which includes: purification of ferrous chloride solutions from impurities; separation of crystals $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - saturation of the initial solution by evaporating it to 40% by volume, cooling and crystallisation at a temperature of 298 K; - dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals by centrifugation; high-temperature hydrolysis of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals at 873 K in a fluidized bed furnace; purification of a steam-dust-gas mixture in a cascade of precipitation cyclones; condensation of the vapour-gas mixture to obtain a circulating hydrochloric acid solution.

As a result, an ultrafine powder was obtained using the technology of high-temperature hydrolysis of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 903 K, the particles have a spherical and rhombic shape, and also have a high magnetic susceptibility.

Conclusion

A technology is developed for processing pyrite concentrates with the extraction of nickel and cobalt, iron and sulphur using dissociating roasting followed by hydrometallurgical processing of cinders. The testing of the extraction technology for the separation of elements, including the processes of refining and concentration of productive solutions, with the extraction of cobalt from the leaching solution up to 99% and the degree of nickel extraction up to 98%, has been carried out.

As a result of processing of ferrous chloride solutions to obtain ultra-dispersed powders of iron oxides by high-temperature hydrolysis, the corresponding technology was elaborated.

For the chemical enrichment of pyrite nickel-containing concentrates the technological flowsheet, presented in Fig. 6, is proposed. The proposed technology makes it possible to obtain rich iron-containing solutions that can be processed to obtain iron and its compounds.

Fig. 6. Technological flowsheet of chemical enrichment of pyrite nickel-containing concentrates

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